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Research Paper

The Therapeutic Role of Aloe Barbadensis Miller Leaf in Managing Asthma and Inflammatory Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Aloe barbadensis Miller is commonly named “Korphad” in Marathi. It is native to Africa and the eastern European continents and spread almost worldwide. The present study reports important secondary metabolites in Aloe barbadensis Miller belonging to the Liliaceae family. It is one of the widely distributed medicinal plants that treat many diseases like diabetes, inflammation, ulcers, tumors, and cancer. The powdered leaf was subjected to ethanolic extraction. The ethanolic extract of Aloe barbadensis Miller was investigated for anti-asthmatic and anti-inflammatory activity in animal models with their phytochemical investigation. The anti-asthmatic activity was studied on clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice as well as histamine-induced bronchospasm in guinea pig, and anti-inflammatory activity was examined using carrageenan-induced paw edema in rat models, at a 200 mg/ kg body weight dose, and 400 mg/ kg body weight.

INTRODUCTION

Asthma is a serious allergic disorder of the respiratory system, marked by inflammation and narrowing of airways. This is a great responsibility for medical treatment. Current therapy for asthma has many serious side effects. Therefore, searching for a new therapeutic agent with no or fewer side effects is needed while most inexpensive for the patients. Due to the availability of strong bioactive chemicals, anti-asthmatic herbal remedies have been employed in traditional medicine and have

demonstrated potential therapeutic anti-asthmatic efficacy. Breathlessness, chest tightness, and wheezing during the paroxysmal attack of bronchial asthma are symptoms brought on by a paroxysmal narrowing of the bronchial airways. Asthma is characterized by inflammation (The airway lining becomes red, swollen, and narrow), obstruction (airway muscles become tightened and it may cause difficulty to get air in and out of the lungs), and hyper-responsiveness (muscles encircled and rapid response on small allergens

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and irritants) of the airway. Generally, patients cough more during sleep and when awake in the morning¹. Asthma affects 10% of the population. Epidemiology will help us study asthma's prevalence, morbidity, and mortality rate. Around 235 million individuals around the world have been affected. Many people die from this deadly disease in many countries due to its high prevalence rate. The number of asthma patients has been increasing day by day². Millions of people have died from asthma. The highest number of patients is in New Zealand, Australia, and the United Kingdom, and the lowest patient rate is in China and Malaysia. About 7% of adults and 15% of children have asthma. In several individuals, inflammation causes frequent episodes of wheezing, shortness of breath, coughing, and chest tightness, particularly at night or in the early morning or after exposure to allergens, cold air, and exercise³. Nowadays asthma is considered similar but differs only based on disease severity. Therefore, treating patients with asthma requires differences in dose, route of intake, or frequency of taking the β 2-adrenoceptor agonist, and corticosteroids essential to manage asthma disease. However, asthma sub-phenotype identification has challenged this view in modern medicinal systems. Over the past two decades, research has identified the fundamental source of asthma is the allergic pathways. As per the National Institute of Health, Asthma is an inflammatory disease that targets the airway's narrowing, resulting in the change of eosinophils, mast cells, lymphocytes, and cytokine levels. The patient with asthma is well known to have greater levels of IgE that bind to the receptor of mast cells and inflammatory products⁴. The antigen-antibody interaction results in the activation of inflammatory cellular reactions⁵ thereby releasing the mediator such as histamine, a prostaglandin that ultimately leads to the contraction of airway smooth muscles. Mast cell plays a key role in the

pathophysiology of asthma and is found in large amounts in the airways of asthmatic patients. Now the inhaled allergens activate sensitized mast cells by binding with IgE molecules present on the surface of mast cells storing lease various bronchoconstrictor mediators. Dendritic cells also process the allergens after being conditioned by the thymic stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP) released by the mast and epithelial cells to release several of the chemokines that draw T helper 2 cells, these cells in turn, induce B cells to produce and secrete IgE antibodies that sensitize mast cells, induce eosinophil mediated inflammation and stimulate mast cell proliferation⁶. *Aloe barbadensis* Miller belongs to the Liliaceae family with thick, green to yellowish green lance-shaped, sticky-juicy, sharp, and edged leaves⁷. Aloe vera grows in dry regions of Africa and the eastern European continents. Aloe vera is probably the most used medicinal plant commercially and the most popular plant around the world⁸. Ethanolic leaf extract of the plant contains vitamins, minerals, enzymes, sugars, anthraquinones, phenolic compounds, lignin, saponins, sterols, amino acids, and salicylic⁹. Aloe vera has many therapeutic effects in wound healing, as well as being anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, etc.¹⁰. This dissertation investigated the anti-asthmatic and Anti-inflammatory activity of the ethanolic extract of *Aloe barbadensis* Miller leaf (EEAB) in experimental animal models namely carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats and also asthma effect in clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice and histamine induce convulsions in guinea pigs.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Chemicals and reagents:

Histamine, Clonidine, chlorpheniramine maleate, ketotifen, ethanol, saline water, carrageenan, diclofenac sodium.

Experimental Animals:

The Albino mice (25-30 g), Wistar rats (150-170 g), and guinea pig (350-400 g) were, housed

in the polypropylene cages at a temperature of 22 ± 2 °C, with 12 h day-light cycle. During whole experiments, animals were fed with a balanced diet and water *ad libitum*. The experimental protocol of the study was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (CPCSEA/IAEC/CP-PL/10/2023) of Sudhakar Naik Institute of Pharmacy, Pusad.

Collection and authentication of Plant material:

The plant was collected from the kitchen gardens of the Umarkhed city of Yavatmal district in December and January. The plant was authenticated by Dr. Ramkrishna Sakhre, Department of Material Science, Ayurvedic College, pusad, yavatmal445204.

Preparation of the extract:

The fresh *Aloe barbadensis miller* leaves were washed thoroughly 2-3 times with distilled water and air-dried. A few of these leaves were chopped into small pieces and ground into a fine powder with the help of a grinder machine, and a mortar pestle and polyethylene bags were used to store them. These bags were kept in the oven for further analysis. The dried powder was extracted with 70% ethanol by using the Soxhlet apparatus.

Phytochemical Screening:

The obtained ethanolic extract was tested for various chemical constituents with the help of qualitative chemical tests ¹¹.

Acute Toxicity Study:

The acute oral toxicity study on the whole leaf and green rind extracts of *A. vera* was conducted according to the 'Up and Down' method described in OECD guideline 425. Nulliparous, non-pregnant female Wistar albino rats were used. For each extract, the animals were randomly divided into 4 groups, each having 3 rats. A single animal was administered a starting dose of 175mg/kg and observed for a period of 48h. The animal was observed continuously for the first 30min post-administration, every 1h for 4h, then once daily for

48h for signs of toxicity including bodyweight variation, salivation, tremors, convulsions, diarrhea, changes in the skin, fur, eyes, and mucous membranes, or death before the next doses of 550, 1750 and 5000mg/kg were administered. In addition, the animals were monitored daily for an additional 12 days for delayed signs of toxicity and mortality. The body weights were taken on day 0, day 7, and day 14. Finally, the LD50 was determined¹².

Evaluation of Anti-Asthmatic Activity:

1. Clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice-

Albino mice will be divided into four groups (n=3). The inducer control group received distilled water (10ml/kg p.o.), The standard group received pheniramine malate (10mg/kg. I.p.). The third and fourth groups will receive EEAB at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight. p.o. respectively. All the groups will receive Clonidine (1mg/kg s.c.) 1 hr after the drug administration and the duration of catalepsy will be measured at (15,30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 min). Evaluation: A decrease in the duration of catalepsy is calculated versus control. Standard and test groups are compared with the control group¹³.

2. Histamine-induced bronchospasm in guinea pigs-

In this method, guinea pigs were kept in a closed chamber and exposed to an aerosol of 0.5% histamine using the nebulizer. The time required to develop pre-convulsive dyspnoea (PCD) was recorded from the time of aerosol exposure to the onset of dyspnoea leading to the appearance of convulsions¹⁴. As soon as pre-convulsive dyspnoea was induced, animals were removed from the chamber and placed in fresh air to recover. Guinea pigs were divided into 4 different groups, with six animals in each group. The control group was orally treated with, 1% tween-80, at the dose of 5 ml/kg, body weight. Test groups received oral treatment of EEAB at doses 200 and 400 mg/kg, body weight, and ketotifen at

a dose of 1 mg/kg, body weight orally was administered to the standard group. All the groups were given a single dose treatment for seven days. The time for the onset of PCD was recorded on day 0 before treatment and on day 7, 2 h after the last dose. The increases in PCD onset time by the animals were calculated by the following formula¹⁵.

Percent increase in PCD

$$\text{time} = [1 - T1/T2 \times 100]$$

Where,

T1 = Time for onset of symptoms before treatment.

T2 = Time for onset of symptoms after treatment.

3. Evaluation of Anti-Inflammatory Activity Study–

I. Carrageenan-induced rat paw edema:

The anti-inflammatory reaction is readily produced in rats in the form of paw edema using carrageenan. The rats were divided into four groups, each consisting of 3 animals. Group I: Control animals received distilled water 10ml/kg p.o. Group II: Animals received standard Diclofenac sodium at the dose of 5mg/kg p.o. Group III: Animals received EEAB at the dose of 200 mg/kg p.o. Group IV: Animals received an EEAB at the dose of 400 mg/kg p.o. After 30 min

of extract administration, 0.1ml of 1% w/v carrageenan was injected into the right hind paw sub-plantar region of each rat. The left paw served as a control for comparison. The paw volumes of both paws of control and extract-treated rats were measured at 30, 60, 90, and 120 min after carrageenan administration". The percentage of edema inhibition for each rat and each group was obtained by using the formula:

$$\text{Anti-inflammatory activity (\%)} = [(VC-Vt)/VC] \times 100$$

Where,

VC = inflammatory increase in paw volume in the control group.

Vt = increase in paw volume in drug-treated animals.

Statistical Analysis:

The result were analysed with Prism Software by GraphPad (version 8.4.2). The results for each category will be expressed as the mean± SEM for each group. Statistical variations were evaluated using One-way variance analysis (ANOVA) accompanied by Dunnett's t-test. Where**** represents significant at $p \leq 0.0001$ as compared with Normal control.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1- Phytochemical analysis of an ethanolic extract of *Aloe barbadensis* Millar

Sr no.	Phytochemicals	Chemical test	Ethanolic extract
1.	Alkaloid	Dragendroff's test	+
2.	Cardiac Glycoside	Keller-Kilani test	+
3.	Reducing sugar	Fehling's test	+
4.	Steroids	Salkowaski test	+
5.	Terpenoids	Vanillin-sulphuric test	-
6.	Carbohydrates	Molish test	+
7.	Amino acids	Ninhydrin test	+
8.	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test	+
9.	Tannins	Ferric Chloride test	+
10.	Saponin	Lead acetate test	+

Plant Name	Aloe barbadensis Millar
<i>Part used</i>	Leaves
Solvent used	Ethanol
Weight of dried leaves	150 gm

Yield	12.7 gm
Percent yield	8.7 %

Acute toxicity study:

All the extracts caused no mortality or behavioral changes in the rats throughout the study. Generally, there was an increase in the animals' body weight throughout the study period.

Therefore, the LD50 was estimated to be above 5000mg/kg for all the extracts.

The percent yield of ethanolic extract of *Aloe barbadensis* Millar:

Table 2 - Percent yield of ethanolic extract of *Aloe barbadensis* Millar

Treatment	Duration of catalepsy in mice (sec)						
	15 min	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min
control	28.60 ± 0.89	73.07 ± 1.92	105.4 ± 3.29	199.7 ± 5.82	221.5 ± 11.37	206.2 ± 2.45	192.6 ± 1.70
Standard (1 mg/kg)	10.10 ± 1.92	21.97 ± 2.55	52.57 ± 6.02	57.57 ± 11.63	63.0 ± 4.17	62.20 ± 3.06	67.90 ± 0.79***
EEAB (200 mg/kg)	25.73 ± 1.25	62.30 ± 2.35	91.43 ± 4.74	109.7 ± 17.16	133.3 ± 2.08	105.8 ± 1.61	98.10 ± 1.25 ^{nsns}
EEAB (400mg/kg)	16.80 ± 2.44	55.17 ± 3.62	60.93 ± 3.50	70.0 ± 13.34	76.73 ± 5.98	72.50 ± 1.76	70.17 ± 1.07***##

Table 3 -Clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice

Values were expressed as mean ± SEM (n=3). The statistical significance between means was analyzed using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Tukey test.

**Statistically significant at (p<0.001),

***Statistically significant at (p<0.0001) when compared with inducer control group I.

##Statistically Significant at P<0.001, when compared with standard group II.

ns indicate non significant.

Histamine induced bronchospasm**Fig no.1- Histogram of the effect of EEAB on Clonidine-induced catalepsy in mice.**

In the above method, EEAB shows a significant effect as compared to the Inducer control ($P < 0.0001$). The catalepsy occurrences mean the animal shows symptoms like the rigidity of body and tightness of the body, So the dose of

400mg/kg, was found to be reduced in the duration of action of catalepsy after 150 min. The standard ketotifen was found to be highly significant at all intervals ($p < 0.0001$).

Table 4 - Histamine-induced bronchospasm in guinea pigs

Sr. no.	Treatment	Dose	PCT Mean \pm SEM (sec)	% protection
1.	Control	10 ml/kg	2.83 \pm 0.24	-
2.	Standard (ketotifen)	1mg/kg	8.89 \pm 0.43***	68%
3.	EEAB	200mg/kg	3.18 \pm 0.23 ^{ns}	11%
4.	EEAB	400mg/kg	5.47 \pm 0.31 ^{###}	48%

Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3). The statistical significance between means was analysed using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Tukey test.

Fig no. 2- Histogram of the Effect of EEAB on histamine-induced bronchospasm in the rat.

*Statistically significant at ($p < 0.05$), **Statistically significant at ($p < 0.001$). ***Statistically significant at ($p < 0.0001$) when compare with inducer control group I.

###Statistically Significant at $P < 0.001$ when compared to the standard group (Group-II). ns indicate non significance.

Table 5 - Carrageenan-induced rat paw edema

Treatments	Increase in Paw volume in ml				% inhibition
	% inhibition of paw edema				
	1 hr	2 hrs	3 hrs	4 hrs	
Disease Control (10 ml/kg)	0.40 \pm 0.02	0.42 \pm 0.02	0.42 \pm 0.02	0.47 \pm 0.02	-
Standard (Diclofenac sodium 5mg/kg)	0.19 \pm 0.01	0.17 \pm 0.014***	0.14 \pm 0.013	0.12 \pm 0.013***	74.46%
EEAB (200mg/kg)	0.31 \pm 0.01	0.28 \pm 0.01 [#]	0.25 \pm 0.017	0.24 \pm 0.01 ^{##}	48.93%
EEAB (400 mg/kg)	0.24 \pm 0.014	0.21 \pm 0.016 ^{##}	0.21 \pm 0.014	0.17 \pm 0.016 ^{***##}	63.82%

Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM (n=3). The statistical significance between means was analyzed using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Tukey test.

*Statistically significant at (p<0.05), **Statistically significant at (p<0.001), ***Statistically significant at (p<0.0001), when compared with disease control group I.

#Statistically Significant at P<0.05, ##Statistically Significant at P<0.001, when compared with standard group II. ns indicate non significant.

After exposure to histamine aerosol animals started showing PCT. Animals in the control group showed Pre-convulsion at around 2.83 seconds. A high dose of 400 mg/kg shows a significant p<0.0001 increase in Pre-convulsion time. The extract of higher doses showed an inhibitory effect on pre-convulsive breathing or pre-convulsive dyspnoea. The results of the study suggested that the ethanolic extract of *A. vera* shows a significant inhibitory effect on pre-convulsion symptoms like dyspnoea, asphyxia, convulsion, etc.

Fig no. 3- Histogram of Anti-inflammatory activity of EEAB on Carrageenan-induced rat paw edema.

In carrageenan, a paw edema model significance was observed after 2 hr in Standard treated (p<0.001 to p<0.0001) as Compared to the Control group and standard group. a marked reduction in paw edema compared to control after 2 hrs, an anti-inflammatory effect seen. Extract [dose 400mg/kg] % inhibition (63.82%), Extract [dose 200 mg/kg] % inhibition (48.93%), and Diclofenac sodium [dose 5 mg/kg] % inhibition also impaired the oedema formation, but this anti-inflammatory effect was much stronger (74.46%).

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